

Consumer Perception on Digital Marketing Gender Based Analysis

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Abstract : *Digitization being a key economic driver in the present world it is important to integrate the economy by creating digital markets. This revolution has been aided by the advent of the Internet in a big way. Internet is fast changing the way people used to do things. Naturally, the same would have an impact on the advertisers. The Internet has been accepted as the most powerful media for advertising due to the absence of geographical barriers. The advent of the Internet and its subsequent acceptance has once again challenged the traditional forms of advertising. Advertisers are trying to use the 'net' to advertise their products and hence 'net' their customers. Thus, with the Internet gaining prominence, advertising equations are fast changing. The present paper is guided by the objective to study the impact of online marketing on Indian economy, the growth pace and its benefits and challenges.*

Keywords : Digital Marketing, Consumer Perception.

Introduction :

Online marketing is the wave of the future. Internet marketing, also referred to as e-Marketing, online marketing or Digital Marketing, is the marketing of products or services over the Internet. Internet marketing ties together creative and technical aspects of the Internet, including design, development, advertising, and sale. The Internet has brought many unique benefits to marketing, one of which being lower costs for the distribution of information and media to a global audience. The interactive nature of Internet marketing, both in terms of providing instant response and eliciting responses, is a unique quality of the medium. Internet marketing is sometimes considered to have a broader scope because it not only refers to digital media such as the Internet, e-mail, and wireless media; however, Internet marketing also includes management of digital customer data and electronic customer relationship management (ECRM) systems.

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Definition

“Digital Marketing is the process of promoting a brand, products or services over the Internet. Its broad scope includes email marketing, electronic customer relationship management and any promotional activities that are done via wireless media.”

Objectives of the Study :

The basic objective of present study is to have a macro re-look at the scenario of Digital Market in India. However, study is guided by the following sub Objectives.

- To study the digital marketing.
- To know the various factors that influence digital consumer perception.
- To study the impact of the digital marketing antecedents on the consumer buying behaviour.

Methodology of the Study :

For the purpose of this research,

- **Primary Data :** Primary data were sourced with the use of questionnaire. The questionnaire comprised close-ended questions only. The completed questionnaires were drawn based on the research questions under study. Quantitative research is designed to disclose a target audience's range of behavior and perception that drive it with specific references. Data collection and survey analyzes done through Google Form questionnaire survey collection.
- **Secondary Data :** Secondary data can play a substantial role in explanatory phase; this data will be collected through secondary sources like research reports, websites, standard text books, newspapers, magazines etc.

Hypothesis :

H0 : There is no significant difference between Male and Female (Gender Factor) responses towards digital marketing.

H1 : There is a significant difference between Male and Female (Gender Factor) responses towards digital marketing.

Review of Literature :

According to Chaffey (2011), digital media marketing involves “encouraging customer communications on company’s own website or through its social presence”. Digital marketing, electronic marketing, e-marketing and Internet marketing are all similar terms which, simply put, refer to “marketing online whether via websites, online ads, opt-in emails, interactive kiosks, interactive TV or mobiles” (Chaffey & Smith, 2008). Giese and Gote (2000) finds that customer information satisfaction (CIS) for digital marketing can be conceptualized as a sum of affective response of varying intensity that follows consumption and is stimulated by focal aspects of sales activities, information systems (websites), digital products/services, customer support, after-sales service and company culture. Waghmare (2012) pointed out that many countries in Asia are taking advantage of e-commerce through opening up, which is essential for promoting competition and diffusion of Internet technologies.

Elements of Digital Marketing

There are various elements by which digital marketing is formed. All forms operate through electronic devices. The most important elements of digital marketing are given below :

- **Online advertising :** Online advertising is a very important part of digital marketing. It is also called internet advertising through which company can deliver the message about the products or services. Internet-based advertising provides the content and ads that best matches to consumer interests. Publishers put about their products or services on their websites so that consumers or users get free information. Advertisers should place more effective and relevant ads online. Through online advertising, company well controls its budget and it has full control on time.
- **Email Marketing :** When message about the products or services is sent through email to the existing or potential consumer, it is defined as email marketing. Direct digital marketing is used to send ads, to build brand and customer loyalty, to build customer trust and to make brand awareness. Company can promote its products and services by using this element of digital marketing easily. It is relatively low cost comparing to advertising or other forms of media exposure. Company can bring complete attention of the customer by creating attractive mix of graphics, text and links on the products and services.
- **Social Media :** Today, social media marketing is one of the most important digital marketing channels. It is a computer-based tool that allows people to create, exchange ideas, information and pictures about the company's product or services. According to Nielsen, internet users continue to spend more time with social media sites than any other type. Social media marketing networks include Facebook, Twitter, LinkedIn and Google+. Through Facebook, company can promote events concerning product and services, run promotions that comply with the Facebook guidelines and explore new opportunities. Through Twitter, company can increase the awareness and visibility of their brand. It is the best tool for the promotion of company's products and services. In LinkedIn, professionals write their profile and share information with others. Company can develop their profile in LinkedIn so that the professionals can view and can get more information about the company's product and services. Google+ is also social media network that is more effective than other social media like Facebook, Twitter. It is not only simple.
- **Text Messaging :** Social media network but also it is an authorship tool that links web-content directly with its owner. It is a way to send information about the products and services from cellular and smart phone devices. By

using phone devices, company can send information in the form of text (SMS), pictures, video or audio (MMS). Using SMS for campaigns get faster and more substantial results. Under this technique, companies can send marketing messages to their customers in real-time, any time and can be confident that the message will be seen. Company can create a questionnaire and obtain valuable customer feedback essential to develop their products or services in future.

- **Affiliate Marketing** : Affiliate marketing is a type of performance-based marketing. In this type of marketing, a company rewards affiliates for each visitor or customer they bring by marketing efforts they create on behalf of company. Industry has four core players: the merchant (also known as “retailer” or “brand”), the network, the publisher (also known as “the affiliate”) and the customer. There are two ways to approach affiliate marketing: Company can offer an affiliate program to others or it can sign up to be another business’s affiliate. If company wants to drive an affiliate program, then, the company owner has to pay affiliates a commission fee for every lead or sale they drive to company’s website. Company’s main goal here is to find affiliates who can reach untapped markets.
- **Search Engine Optimization (SEO)** : Search engine optimization (SEO) is the process of affecting the visibility of a website or a web page in a search engine’s “natural” or un-paid (“organic”) search results. In general, the earlier (or higher ranked on the search results page), and more frequently a website appears in the search result list, the more visitors it will receive from the search engine users. SEO may target different kinds of search including image search, local search, video search, academic search, news search and industry-specific vertical search engines.
- **Pay Per Click (PPC)** : Pay-per-click marketing is a way of using search engine advertising to generate clicks to your website rather than “earning” those clicks organically. Pay per click is good for searchers and advertisers. It is the best way for company’s ads since it brings low cost and greater engagement with the products and services.

Consumer Behaviour :

Consumer behaviour is defined as a study to gain insight how individuals or groups buy, use and dispose of products, services or experiences to satisfy their needs. The decision making of the consumer is determined by the pre-purchase

behaviour, which is preceded by the intention to buy/consume and a host of other antecedent factors. Some of these factors are intrinsic to the consumer like the personal aspects – beliefs/evaluation based attitude towards the act (purchase), while the extrinsic variables like social aspects - subjective norms and the perceived/actual behavioural control etc., conditioned within the situational construct, influence the consumer's behavioural intention. Attitude-behaviour consistency has been of great interest to researchers since the 1930s. The consumer decision-making process is a sequential and repetitive series of psychological and physical activities ranging from problem recognition to post-purchase behaviour. Market dominated variables (such as the environment and advertising) and consumer-dominated variables (such as needs, motives, personality and perception) simultaneously interact to influence the consumer's purchasing decision. Consumer decision process is the decision making process undertaken by consumers in regard to a potential market transaction before, during and after the purchase of the product or service. More generally decision making process is the cognitive process of selecting a course of action from among multiple alternatives. Common examples include shopping, deciding what to eat etc. Decision making is said to be a psychological construct. This means that although we can never see a decision, we can infer from observable actions, we assume that people have made a commitment to effect the action. In general there are two ways of analysing consumer buying decisions. viz.,

Economic models : These models are largely quantitative and are based on the assumptions of rationality and perfect knowledge. The consumer is seen to their maximum utility.

Psychological models : These models concentrate on physiological and cognitive processes such as motivation and need recognition. They are qualitative rather than quantitative and build on sociological factors like cultural influences and family influences.

The Buying Decision Process :

The buyer decision making process consists of the following steps

1. **Need Recognition :** The buying process starts when the buyer recognizes problem or need triggered by internal or external stimuli¹ According to the buyers' decisions are affected by numerous stimuli from their environment. The commercial environment consists of the marketing activities of various firms by which they attempt to communicate the buyers² From the buyer's point of view, these communications come to the buyer through either brand objects such as price, quality, service, distinctiveness and availability, or

through brand representation such as media or salesman. The buyers are also stimulated by their social environment which provides a purchase decision and the most obvious example is word-of-mouth (WOM) communication. The significance of WOM in influencing consumer decision making has been well recognised in marketing and advertising literature.

2. **Information Search :** The buyer may enter an active information search by looking for reading material, asking friends, going online and visiting shops to learn about the active seeking of information occurs when the senses ambiguity of brand meaning and that exists, because the buyer is not certain and has not learned enough yet about the purchase outcome of each alternative (Kotler et al (2009) have identified major information sources to which the consumers are Personal family, friends, neighbours, acquaintances, Commercial advertising, websites, salespeople, dealers, packaging, displays, Experiential handling, examining, using the product.
3. **Evaluation of Alternatives :** Howard and Sheth (1969) state that through a learning process, the buyers obtain and store knowledge of each brand's potential and then ranks them according to potential to satisfy their needs, so this is a set of alternatives to be evaluated the beliefs as a descriptive thought that a person holds about something and the attitudes as a person's enduring favourable and unfavourable evaluations, emotional feeling and action tendencies toward some idea.
4. **Purchase :** The evaluation of alternative brands may lead the consumer to form preferences for brands in the choice set. Although the consumers form brand evaluations, there can be intervening factors between the purchase intention and the purchase decision. The purchase decision may also be subject to various anticipated situational factors such as temporary cash-flow problems, time availability and stock levels. In most circumstances, a consumer's decisions can be associated with the perceived risk and the consumer may modify, postpone and avoid a purchase decision because of the perceived risk. The consumers may perceive many types of risk in their buying decision.

Functional risk the product does not perform up to expectations. *Physical risk* the product poses a threat to the physical well-being or health of the user or others. *Financial risk* the product is not worth the price paid. *Social risk* the product results in embarrassment from others. *Psychological risk* the product does not conform to the consumer's perceived self-image. *Time risk* the failure of the product results in an opportunity cost of finding another satisfactory

product. The consumers can reduce the uncertainty and negative consequences of risk by gathering information from friends and preferences for national brand, so the marketers should understand the factors of a feeling of risk in consumers and provide information to reduce perceived risk.

5. **Post-purchase Behaviour :** The buyer's satisfaction is a function of the closeness between the buyer's expectations and the product's perceived performance. If the performance is below expectations, then the customer will be dissatisfied and will suffer from the mismatch, if it meets expectations, then the customer will be satisfied, if it exceeds the expectations, the customer will be delighted. The word-of-mouth transmissions are influential in the pre- and post-purchase stages. In the post-purchase period, consumer word-of-mouth transmissions provide informal communications which are directed at other consumers about the ownership, usage and experiences of goods and services.

Data Analysis and Interpretation :

Table-1 : It is understood from the above table that 52.5% are Male respondents and 47.5% are Female respondents. Most of the male and female respondents fall under the age group of 21-30. Employees occupy the major portion of the respondents in the survey. Under qualification group most of the respondents are post graduates and 66.25% of the total respondents falls under less than 20000 income group.

Table-2 : As per the Data shown in table-2 regarding the awareness on digital marketing, the difference of mean value between genders is 18.75, the t-test value is 2.457 which is higher than the critical value 2.35 and the p-value is 0.046. Therefore the result of t-test about the awareness on Digital marketing is not significant and hence Null hypothesis is accepted and Alternative hypothesis is rejected. For the respondents opinion on availability of online information about products, the difference of mean value between genders is 4.25, the t-test value is 0.11 which is lower than the critical value 2.35 and the p-value is -1.53. Therefore the result of t-test about the availability of online information is significant and hence alternate hypothesis is accepted and null hypothesis is rejected.

The calculated ANOVA values for the issues relating to products usually preferred to purchase, sources used to gather information, payment methods adopted and reasons for choosing online purchases the p-value is below the critical value 0.05, Therefore Null hypothesis is accepted and alternative hypothesis is rejected.

Data Analysis and Interpretation
Table-1 : Demographic profile of respondents

Respondents age wise	Age / Category	Male				female				Grand Total		
		15-20	21-30	31-40	> 40	Sub.Total	15-20	21-30	31-40		> 40	Sub.Total
	Male	13	23	6	0	42	3	23	7	5	38	80
Occupation	Category	Male				female				Grand Total		
		15-20	21-30	31-40	> 40	Sub.Total	15-20	21-30	31-40	> 40	Sub.Total	Grand Total
	student	12	7	0	0	19	2	3	0	0	5	24
	Employee	0	9	6	0	15	0	12	3	1	16	31
	profession	0	2	0	0	2	0	2	4	4	10	12
	business	1	3	0	0	4	1	0	0	0	1	5
	others	0	2	0	0	2	0	6	0	0	6	8
Sub.Total	13	23	6	0	42	3	23	7	5	38	80	
qualification	Category	Male				female				Grand Total		
		15-20	21-30	31-40	> 40	Sub.Total	15-20	21-30	31-40	> 40	Sub.Total	Grand Total
	SSC or Below	1	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	1
	intermediate	4	4	0	0	8	0	0	0	0	0	8
	graduation	8	7	2	0	17	2	9	0	0	11	28
	PG	0	12	4	0	16	1	14	7	5	27	43
	others	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Sub.Total	13	23	6	0	42	3	23	7	5	38	80	
Monthly income	Category	Male				female				Grand Total		
		15-20	21-30	31-40	> 40	Sub.Total	15-20	21-30	31-40	> 40	Sub.Total	Grand Total
	less than 20k	12	17	0	0	29	2	19	3	0	24	53
	20k-40k	1	6	5	0	12	1	4	4	4	13	25
	40k-60k	0	0	1	0	1	0	0	0	1	1	2
	Above 60k	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
	Sub.Total	13	23	6	0	42	3	23	7	5	38	80

Source: Primary Data

Table-2 : Responses towards Digital Marketing

S.no	Particulars	Category	Male						Female						Grand Total	Annova / t-test Results
			15-20	21-30	31-40	>40	Sub. Tot	15-20	21-30	31-40	>40	Sub. Tot				
1	Awareness on Digital Marketing	Yes	13	20	6	0	39	2	22	7	5	36	75	m value=18.75 P(T<=t)one-tail=2.457 P value=0.046t Critical one-tail = 2.3533		
		No	0	3	0	0	3	1	1	0	0	2	5			
		Sub. Tot	13	23	6	0	42	3	23	7	5	38	80			
2	Products usually preferred to purchase Digitally	Electronic items	4	9	6	0	19	0	8	0	2	10	29	F-Value-2.1848 P-value-0.09095 F-crit 2.6414		
		Apparels	1	4	0	0	5	0	5	5	1	11	16			
		Jewellery	0	0	0	0	0	1	1	0	0	2	2			
		Bookings	5	7	0	0	12	1	4	2	2	9	21			
		Others	3	3	0	0	6	1	5	0	0	6	12			
		Sub. Tot	13	23	6	0	42	3	23	7	5	38	80			
3	Frequency of Online shopping By respondents	Regularly	4	6	2	0	12	1	2	1	3	7	19	f-Value1.9026 value-0.1520 F-crit 2.946		
		Rarely	3	4	1	0	8	0	4	1	0	5	13			
		Need base	4	12	3	0	19	1	14	2	1	18	37			
		Offers& discounts	2	1	0	0	3	1	3	3	1	8	11			
		Sub. Tot	13	23	6	0	42	3	23	7	5	38	80			
		Search engines	6	8	3	0	17	1	6	2	1	10	27			
4	Sources to gather information	Product catalogues	1	5	2	0	8	0	3	1	2	6	14	f-Value-4.2445 value-0.0032 F-crit 2.4376		
		Friends& Family	5	7	1	0	13	2	7	2	2	13	26			
		Advertisements	1	2	0	0	3	0	2	2	0	4	7			
		Promotional mails	0	1	0	0	1	0	3	0	0	3	4			
		Others.	0	0	0	0	0	0	2	0	0	2	2			
		Sub. Tot	13	23	6	0	42	3	23	7	5	38	80			

5	Rating of online products	Excellent	6	2	2	0	10	0	4	2	1	7	17	M value=4.25 P(T<t) tail=0.11 pvalue=-1.53 one-tail = 2.35 t Critical
		Good	7	21	4	0	32	3	19	5	4	31	63	
		Sub. Tot	13	23	6	0	42	3	23	7	5	38	80	
6	Payment Methods adopted by Consumers	Debit Card	6	9	3	0	18	1	13	5	1	20	38	f-Value14.1006 P-value-0.01526 F-crit 2.9466
		Credit Card	0	0	1	0	1	0	0	0	2	2	3	
		Net Banking	1	0	2	0	3	0	0	0	1	1	4	
7	Frequency of visits to Online stores during last 12 months	Cash on Delivery	6	13	1	0	20	2	10	2	1	15	35	F-Value-0.6652 value-0.6204 crit -2.6416
		Sub. Tot	13	22	7	0	42	3	23	7	5	38	80	
		1 – 2times	4	3	2	0	9	0	8	0	1	9	18	
8	Reasons for choosing online purchases	3 – 5 times	3	6	1	0	10	1	6	4	2	13	23	F-Value-2.1848 P-value-0.09095 F-crit 2.6414
		6 – 10 times	1	7	0	0	8	0	6	2	1	9	17	
		10 – 20 times	2	5	1	0	8	1	1	0	1	3	11	
9	Consumers perception of risk in Digital Purchases	>20 times	3	2	2	0	6	1	2	1	0	5	11	F-Value-0.0165 P-value-0.0462 crit -2.9466
		Sub. Tot	13	23	6	0	42	3	23	7	5	38	80	
		Convenience	4	9	6	0	19	0	8	0	2	10	29	
9	Consumers perception of risk in Digital Purchases	Quick Delivery	1	4	0	0	5	0	5	5	1	11	16	F-Value-0.0165 P-value-0.0462 crit -2.9466
		Online goods	0	0	0	0	0	1	1	0	0	2	2	
		Global markets	5	7	0	0	12	1	4	2	2	9	21	
9	Consumers perception of risk in Digital Purchases	24x7 Shopping	3	3	0	0	6	1	5	0	0	6	12	F-Value-0.0165 P-value-0.0462 crit -2.9466
		Sub. Tot	13	23	6	0	42	3	23	7	5	38	80	
		touch & feel	6	13	5	0	24	0	3	4	2	9	33	
9	Consumers perception of risk in Digital Purchases	Misuse of personal details	6	4	0	0	10	3	1	0	3	7	17	F-Value-0.0165 P-value-0.0462 crit -2.9466
		mis-match of delivery	3	3	2	0	8	3	7	1	0	11	19	
		Others	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	1	
		Sub. Tot	15	20	7	0	42	6	11	6	5	28	80	

Source: Primary Data

Results in relating to frequency of online shopping visits, the p-value is higher than the critical value. Therefore Null Hypothesis is rejected and alternative hypothesis is accepted.

Findings and Conclusions:

1. In the study it was found that male respondents are more than the female respondents who were responded for online responses about awareness on digital marketing for designed questionnaire.
2. Study reveals that electronic items are preferred more by the respondents among the online products
3. It is also understood from the study that the respondents are not attracted towards offers and product promotions and purchase according to the need.
4. Based on the survey online source of product information is gathered from internet search engines followed by word of mouth.
5. Debit cards and cash on delivery are the most adopted payments methods by the respondents.
6. Study reveals that reasons for choosing online purchases by consumers are Convenience and access to global markets.
7. It can be understood from the study that the risk factors in the digital purchases are mostly no possibility to touch and feel the product, mis-match of delivery and mis-use of personal details of consumers.
8. The overall satisfaction of the consumers on the digital purchases is rated as good.

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Footnotes

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